

FEATURES OF HIGHER CORTICAL ACTIVITY IN CHILDREN WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDERS

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Abstract. *Autism spectrum disorders (ASD) in children hold significant relevance both in neurology and psychiatry. The reasons for this include their relatively high prevalence, the lack of unified concepts regarding etiology and pathogenesis, as well as the challenges of accurate diagnosis and comprehensive corrective therapy. Cognitive impairments, according to many authors, accompany this pathology and are observed in every second affected child. The present article provides an analysis of the occurrence of higher cortical function disorders in children with autism spectrum disorders.*

In the study, 240 children aged 3 to 11 years diagnosed with autism spectrum disorders (ASD) were examined. Children aged 3 to 6 years accounted for 40.4% of the patients, while 59.5% of the patients examined were aged 7 to 11 years. Neuropsychological assessment was conducted using integrative neuropsychological testing, employing an adapted examination methodology by A.R. Luria for pediatric neurologists. The analysis of the testing allowed for a clearer understanding of the severity of cognitive impairments in this category of patients, revealing a diffuse disorganization of optimal brain functioning. This was reflected in severe speech and socio-behavioral disorders.

Keywords: *autism disorders, children, cognitive functions, neuropsychological testing.*

At present, autism spectrum disorders (ASD) have become highly significant and represent one of the priority areas for comprehensive scientific study. The main reason for this is the annual increase in the number of patients diagnosed with ASD. Autism spectrum disorders are a pathological continuum characterized by deviations in social interaction and communication, that is, in the process of interaction and information exchange with peers and adults [1].

Various theories in the literature explain the causes of autism disorders, including biological, social, and psychological factors. There are also assumptions that explain the symptoms of autism disorders as consequences of deviations in cognitive activity and the emotional sphere. Cognitive changes in children with ASD are noted in every second child. Patients with autism often lack the skills to connect multiple elements, meaning signals received from different sensory organs are not integrated into a cohesive whole. This leads to a deficit in perception and understanding of the surrounding world, significant problems in recognizing the thoughts, intentions, and feelings of both peers and adults. At the cognitive level, this manifests in two ways: first, the child with autism does not understand what they perceive; second, they are unable to adequately reflect and plan their responses [2,3].

The abilities of cognitive functioning inherent to every person have individual degrees of development. These abilities are necessary to understand what we see or hear, to read or write text, perform arithmetic operations, plan the day, analyze a situation, and respond to it. Overall, the cognitive sphere encompasses all the daily activities of an individual [4].

According to many authors, the majority of patients with autism disorders exhibit pronounced deviations in the formation of cognitive functions. Based on this, the following variants of cognitive development are highlighted in children with ASD: 1) profaned, marked by a dissociated combination of normative and advanced development with components of delay; 2) deficient, with a delay relative to normative development in some components; 3) regressive-defective, with a delay relative to normative development in all components. These deviations are observed in children from infancy [2,5]. It is also worth noting that cognitive activity disorders in this category of children are a secondary product of autistic behavior, which significantly inhibits the formation and maturation of intelligence [6].

The formation of cognitive activity in children with autism disorders requires special attention, as it is a primary condition for developing the need and sense of necessity for fundamental knowledge, which creates conditions for further education and individual growth. The main cognitive areas include: attention, memory and imagination, sensation and perception, and thinking. A deeper study of each of these areas reveals, for example, that attention in children with ASD is characterized by its instability; children find it very difficult to focus on things outside their area of interest. They struggle to maintain attention on things that do not interest them at the moment. Overall, attention in such children is selective and short-lived. As Lebedinsky V.V. (1990) pointed out, attention in children with ASD is never normal; it either fades very quickly or is so unstable that concentration is out of the question. Memory in children with autism disorders is mechanical in nature; information is absorbed in whole blocks and is not processed. Imagination in these children is also distorted; it either manifests concretely and sparingly or in the form of painful, unnatural fantasies and specific fears. Thinking in children with ASD is so-called “visual,” meaning their reflections occur in “pictures.” They lack the ability to actively process and generalize the received information, use their abilities and skills, and find it difficult to comprehend the chronology of events, their causal relationships. All this is explained by the need for consistency in their environment. Sensation and perception in autistic children also have their own peculiarities. Their spatial orientation is often disrupted. They often cannot figure out how to get from the store to home or their apartment, despite performing this operation almost every day. During play or other activities, they pay more attention not to the object as a whole but to its components [7,8].

Currently, there are many methods used in working with children suffering from autism spectrum disorders. All of them aim, to some extent, at a detailed study of all the basic functional abilities of the child, considering the multifaceted nature of the disorders and the delay in the development of various functional areas of the brain. Methods applied in working with children with ASD should provide a detailed assessment of all main functional spheres, given the comprehensive nature of the disorders and the asynchrony in the development of different functional areas and skills [9,10]. The goal of all methods is to investigate the issues of deviant development through the prism of neuropsychological testing methods to address problems related to school delays, speech development levels, ontogeny issues, and the analysis of biological and psychosocial factors in child development [11,12]. A.V. Semenovich (2002) stated that a fundamental component of neuropsychological diagnostics is understanding the directions and causal features of the ontogenetic process. Furthermore, the author emphasizes the importance of considering the personal differences of children influenced by endo- and exogenous factors [1].

Thus, autism spectrum disorders represent a group of practically identical syndromes, though of heterogeneous origin. Cognitive manifestations in ASD are most distinctly presented in Kanner's and Asperger's syndromes, although they differ in severity. Timely neuropsychological examination of this category of children will allow for a clearer understanding of the mechanisms of cognitive activity deviations, cerebral structure dysfunctions responsible for cognitive functions, and, finally, to adequately determine strategies and methods of corrective-therapeutic work.

Research Objective: To study the characteristics of cognitive activity disorders in children with autism spectrum disorders.

Materials and Methods: To successfully achieve the set goal, we examined 240 children aged 3 to 11 years diagnosed with autism spectrum disorders (ASD). Children aged 3 to 6 years accounted for 40.4% of the patients. Patients aged 7 to 11 years made up 59.5% of the examined cases.

For the assessment of neuropsychological status, a control group was formed, consisting of 60 patients without any signs of autism spectrum disorders, matched by gender and age. Among them, there were 32 boys (53.3%) and 28 girls (46.7%) (**Table 1**).

Table 1

Distribution of examined patients by age (according to the classification of N.P. Gundobin, modified by A.V. Mazurin and I.M. Vorontsov, 1985) and gender.

Indicator	Categories	Gender		p
		Boys	Girls	
Age group	3-6	77 (41,2)	20 (37,7)	0,652
	7-11	110 (58,8)	33 (62,3)	

*– the differences in indicators are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

When comparing age groups by gender, we did not find significant differences ($p = 0.652$) (method used: Pearson's Chi-square test).

All children included in the study were divided into the following groups:

Group I consisted of children with Kanner's syndrome (F 84.0) – 129 patients (53.8%).

Group II included patients with Asperger's syndrome (so-called high-functioning autism, F 84.5) – 111 patients (46.2%) (**Table 2**).

Table 2

Diagnosis verification was based not only on the ICD-10 criteria
Distribution of patients with autism spectrum disorders by groups.

	Categories	Abs.	95% CI
Kanner's syndrome	129	53,8	47,2 – 60,2
Asperger's syndrome	111	46,2	39,8 – 52,8

*– the differences in indicators are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

A neurological examination was performed using a standard methodology, which included a detailed clinical and neurological assessment following a standard scheme. The severity of autism spectrum disorders was determined using the Childhood Autism Rating Scale (CARS) – a rating scale for childhood autism.

Neuropsychological examination of children with ASD was assessed based on the results of integrative neuropsychological testing using the adapted examination methodology by A.R.

Luria for pediatric neurologists. The neuropsychological assessment method included the evaluation of the following cognitive functions: dynamic, kinesthetic, and spatial praxis; auditory-motor coordination; stereognosis; visual gnosis; speech; auditory-verbal, and visual memory.

The obtained results were statistically processed using Statistics 8.0. Fisher's exact test and Pearson's Chi-square test were used to compare the distribution of qualitative indicators in the study group of children. Data reliability was established at a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion.

At the testing stage, almost all patients with autism spectrum disorders exhibited a negative reaction. Some children refused to complete the tasks, making it quite difficult to establish contact and engage them in the study. Testing showed that a common characteristic among all patients was a limitation in voluntary control, as well as a deficiency in the development of various components of higher cortical activity (Table 3).

Table 3.

Analysis of the occurrence of higher cortical function impairments in children with autism spectrum disorders.

Categories	Group		P
	KS	AS	
Kinesthetic praxis	54 (41,9)	20 (18,0)	< 0,001*
Spatial praxis	70 (54,3)	4 (3,6)	< 0,001*
Dynamic praxis	97 (75,2)	20 (18,0)	< 0,001*
Auditory-motor coordination	107 (82,9)	30 (27,0)	< 0,001*
Stereognosis	107 (82,9)	32 (28,8)	< 0,001*
Visual gnosis	113 (87,6)	49 (44,1)	< 0,001*
Speech	129 (100,0)	111 (100,0)	–
Auditory-verbal memory	107 (82,9)	77 (69,4)	0,015*
Drawing skills	87 (67,4)	49 (44,1)	< 0,001*

* – The differences in indicators are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The kinesthetic praxis test could not be completed by children in Group I in 41.9% of cases, and by patients in Group II in 18.0% of cases.

When performing the "posture praxis" test, i.e., connecting the index and thumb fingers in a ring, while fully extending the middle and ring fingers or the index and ring fingers, this category of children exhibited deviations in the kinesthetic basis of movement.

They were unable to find the necessary movement components, began fidgeting with their fingers, and attempted to use their other hand. Their finger movements were spontaneous and diffuse, and in addition to the required fingers, other unintended fingers were also extended.

An analysis of kinesthetic movement disorders, which were identified in the right hand or bilaterally, may indicate insufficient function of the left parietal lobe. If the impairment was observed in the left hand, this suggested right parietal lobe dysfunction.

Additionally, some children incorrectly positioned their hand in space, reproducing a so-called "mirror posture", meaning that instead of demonstrating the index and middle fingers, they showed the ring and little fingers. These deviations confirmed dysfunction in visual-spatial movement organization, indicating a deficiency in the functions of both the left and right parietal lobes.

The next test required the child to perform movements based on a tactile model with their eyes closed.

Among the Kanner's syndrome group, 40.0% of patients failed to complete the task, compared to 15% of children in the Asperger's syndrome group. Patients who struggled with the task mostly reproduced the posture using only their right hand, while ignoring their left hand. These deviations confirmed unilateral spatial agnosia and demonstrated dysfunction of the midline structures, corpus callosum, and the temporo-parieto-occipital region of the right hemisphere. Similarly, to the first test, children took a long time to find the correct set of movements, fidgeted with their fingers, and tried to use their other hand. Most patients had great difficulty transitioning to a new posture, repeatedly performing a previous movement, demonstrating motor inertia. If these disorders were more pronounced in the right hand or bilaterally, the functional deficit was primarily localized in the left frontal lobe. If the described disorders were most prominent when performing the test with the left hand, then the dysfunction was primarily located in the right frontal lobe. The final kinesthetic praxis test was the posture transfer task, which was also performed by children with their eyes closed. 41.0% of patients from the Kanner's syndrome group and 17% of patients from the Asperger's syndrome group failed the task.

If difficulties arose when transferring a posture from right to left, the disorder suggested a deficiency in the function of the left parietal lobe. If difficulties were observed when transferring a posture from left to right, this indicated dysfunction of the right parietal lobe. Some patients demonstrated bilateral posture transfer disorders, which, in this case, suggested deviations in interhemispheric interaction due to dysfunction in the midline structures and the corpus callosum. When analyzing spatial praxis, 54.3% of children from the Kanner's syndrome group and 3.6% of children from the Asperger's syndrome group failed their tasks. The observed changes during the testing of visual-spatial movement organization, which manifested as an inability to spatially reproduce hand positions and a disruption in left-right orientation, pointed to dysfunction of the parietal lobes of both hemispheres of the brain. Additionally, some patients had difficulty locating specific body parts or facial features, indicating body schema disturbances. Voluntary movement control deficits were identified through expansive execution of the assigned task, difficulty correcting errors, and frontal lobe dysfunctions in both hemispheres. Body schema disorders were observed when a child was unable to identify a specified part of the face or body, which served as evidence of right parietal lobe dysfunction.

Thus, the observed deviations in the visual-spatial organization of movements in ASD patients may confirm insufficient formation of spatial asymmetry concepts.

It is also worth noting that some children were able to correct their mistakes after additional instructions, guiding questions, and improved concentration of attention.

When performing the designated exercises for assessing dynamic praxis, 75.2% of children from the Kanner's syndrome group and 18.0% of patients from the Asperger's syndrome group failed the tasks.

Among the patients who did not complete the assigned tasks, there were isolated, uncoordinated movements, an inability to smoothly transition from one process to another, which indicated a disorder in the dynamic organization of activity.

Fragmentation of the process when performing tasks with the right hand indicated left frontal lobe dysfunction, while fragmentation of movements in the left hand indicated right frontal lobe dysfunction.

Disorders of reciprocal (interdependent) coordination of movements were noted by the inability to simultaneously change the position of both hands. Disorders of reciprocal (interdependent) coordination of movements were noted when children could not simultaneously change the position of both hands, the movement in each hand was performed separately, this demonstrated the dysfunction of the median sections and the interhemispheric commissure. Some patients had a delay in the left or right hands, i.e., decomposition of automated actions. Thus, the delay of the right hand indicated a violation of the functions of the left frontal lobe, and the left hand, respectively, the right frontal lobe. If the left hand was ignored and actions were performed only by the right hand, changes were recorded in the right parietal, median sections and the interhemispheric commissure of the brain. Thus, the study of motor functions in children with autistic disorders revealed changes in the kinesthetic, dynamic and visual-spatial organization of motor processes. The characteristic features of these disorders were the versatility and multiplicity of their signs. In 2016, Grigorieva O.V., in her research, also indicated the presence of a wide range of disorders associated with these types of praxis, while indicating deviations or limited development of the afferent type in the lower postcentral parts of the brain. This is based on a failure in motor differentiation, loss of the motor model, with absolute preservation of the strength of movements and sensitivity. Disorders of kinetic tests indicate a deviation or underdevelopment of the lower parts of the premotor area (efferent zone). With efferent disorders, a failure in the smoothness of motor switching in the complex of voluntary movement is detected, with gross changes, destruction of the motor act occurs, while sensitivity, strength and muscle tone remain absolutely intact [14].

The next test made it possible to analyze auditory-motor coordination skills. In the SC group, 82.9% of patients failed to cope with the task, in the SA group - 27.0% of children. At the same time, the greatest deviations in auditory perception were noted in the form of inability to accurately identify auditory complexes containing a series of successive sounds. Patients could not accurately indicate the number of beats presented, determine whether two rhythms in a row are homogeneous or heterogeneous. All this spoke in favor of dysfunctions occurring in the temporal lobes of the brain. In addition, this category of children had deviations in the form of a disorder of regulation of voluntary actions, this is the inability to perform rhythms according to instructions, but the ability to repeat them by imitation, this also indicated a violation of functions in the temporal lobes [15]. Frequent phenomena were passivity of movements, when children performed extra beats when testing, problems with switching from one rhythm to another with extreme persistence in performing the previous rhythm. These manifestations demonstrated a functional deficit in the frontal lobe of the left hemisphere. Also, most patients who failed the task often forgot the specified rhythm, thereby disrupting the structure of the rhythm. In these cases, one could talk about disturbances in the temporal lobes of the brain. In their studies, Chen J.L., and Konoike N. (2015) also demonstrated complex, coordinated, simultaneous functioning of the auditory, motor and prefrontal areas of the cerebral cortex in optimal processes of perception and reproduction of rhythmic patterns. According to them, auditory-motor synchronization involves both thoroughness of auditory processing for a more accurate assessment of time intervals, and strict motor control over the movement being performed, as well as fine coordination between them [16,17]. According to the stereognosis skills testing, changes in this component were observed in children with Kanner syndrome in 82.9% of cases, and in children with Asperger syndrome in 28.8% of cases. When testing for stereognosis, changes were indicated by failure to

recognize tangible objects (changes in sensory gnosis). In this case, depending on the side of the hand, contralateral deficit of the parietal lobe of the hemisphere was determined. In cases where the patient recognized a tangible thing, but could not correctly indicate its name (amnesic aphasia), one could speak of dysfunction of the temporal lobe of the left hemisphere.

87.6% of children from Group I and 44.1% of patients from Group II failed the visual gnosis testing. Deviations in this testing were detected when children were unable to recognize the images shown, which indicated disorders occurring in the occipital lobes, median sections and interhemispheric commissure of the brain. The most common mistakes were made by patients when interpreting the plot picture. Fragmentation of awareness was noted when they were unable to understand the entire plot presented. Patients, during the so-called storytelling by the picture, gave rather hot-tempered answers, named not the entire object as a whole, but by individual details and, what is important, did not strive to correct the errors indicated by the researcher, which demonstrated the effectiveness of the frontal lobes in the pathological process. Deviations in thinking in this contingent of children could be determined by their lack of understanding of the meaning of the picture shown, which again indicated the insufficiency of the functions of the frontal lobes. Thus, since no visual perception disorders were detected during this testing, which confirmed the preservation of the primary projection zones of the visual analyzer, the deviations of visual gnosis that we identified during the examination were of a secondary nature.

Speech function assessment testing demonstrated that speech disorders to one degree or another are observed in all patients without exception. Thus, in the group of patients with Kanner syndrome, speech deviations were observed in 129 (100.0%) children, a similar picture was in the group with Asperger syndrome - 111 (100.0%). When examining speech, its sensory and motor functioning was affected. Misunderstanding of the instructions presented, the inability to clearly show the named thing indicated the presence of sensory disorders (sensory aphasia), with a pathological process in the temporal lobe of the left hemisphere. In cases where the child had difficulty reproducing individual words, in choosing the right articulation, the child changed letters that sounded close, incorrectly used cases and prepositions, one could talk about disorders of the motor function of speech (kinesthetic aphasia), with the involvement of the frontal and parietal lobes of the left hemisphere in the pathological process. Even Leo Kanner, an Austrian and American psychiatrist known for the first descriptions of childhood autism, noted in his works the characteristic features of speech in children with ASD, such as, for example, its later formation, the presence of echolalia (and at the same time greatly delayed in time), problems in the use of pronouns ("you" instead of "I" and vice versa). However, it is worth noting here that there are studies both confirming the results that speech formation in children with autistic disorders is carried out according to the same scheme as in other groups of patients, and demonstrating differences between speech development in different groups (children with early childhood autism, with Asperger syndrome, with specific speech delay and optimally developing children). For example, in the study of Hajri M., (2022) it was shown that in autistic children, the awareness of words is more limited than the pronunciation of words. But in general, receptive speech in children with ASD was formed earlier than expressive speech, the same thing happened in absolutely healthy children. In addition, the group of patients with autism lagged behind normally developing children in speech development [18]. At the next stage of testing, the functional activity of auditory-verbal memory was assessed, which was checked by memorizing two groups of three words and five words, and repeating words after interference. Changes in auditory-verbal memory

to varying degrees were observed in 82.9% of children with autism and in 69.4% of children with AS. In cases where children were unable to remember a series of three words or distorted them, acoustic-mnemonic aphasia was determined, with damage to the temporal lobe of the left hemisphere. The situation when patients could not remember the words of one series after another series was pronounced, the words were replaced by other words or repetitions, indicated the inertia of traces with the manifestation of stereotypical repetition of the same words (echolalia). In addition, after interference, most of the subjects named a much smaller number of words compared to direct reproduction, and the presented repetitions did not improve the results. These disorders demonstrated the insufficiency of the functions of the frontal, temporal and parietal regions of the left hemisphere. Thus, the greatest number of children examined by us showed a reduction in memory capacity, slow memorization, inertia of speech traces, disorders in the construction of memorized words and deviations in thinking. In addition to the above, this contingent of patients was also characterized by dysfunction of attention according to the modal-nonspecific type. The children were absent-minded, quickly exhausted, could not concentrate for a long time, and when errors were pointed out, they did not try to correct them. In previously published scientific works, the authors also emphasized the predominant disorder of auditory-speech memory in children suffering from autistic disorders. For example, in the study by Habib A., Harris L., (2019), a general decrease in the volume of auditory-verbal memory in preschool-aged children with ASD was found, in addition, a correlation was established between the degree of auditory-verbal memory and the level of speech maturity. The authors demonstrated a decrease in the volume and productivity of memorization [19].

The results of the next test related to drawing showed that 67.4% of children from group I and 44.1% of patients from group II failed to cope with this task. Deviations were manifested by the problematic execution of simple drawings, the omission of significant elements of the image, some patients repeatedly circled the same components of the image, had difficulty switching from one action to another (inertia of movements), all this indicated a dysfunction of the temporal and parietal lobes of the right hemisphere, as well as the frontal lobe of the left hemisphere.

Conclusion. Thus, the analysis of neuropsychological testing made it possible to obtain a more intelligible understanding of the degree of expression of deviations in the activity of higher cerebral functions in children with autism spectrum disorders, where there was a diffuse disorganization of the optimal functioning of the brain, which was reflected in severe speech and social-behavioral disorders. In addition, the neuropsychological study made it possible to determine the differences in the state of higher brain activity in patients with various types of autism disorders. Of the two examined groups of patients, the greatest reliably significant difficulties in testing were experienced by children from the group with Kanner syndrome, and they experienced maximum difficulties in performing almost all test tasks. These deviations indicated a functional deficiency of various cortical areas of the brain, insufficient formation of interhemispheric interactions, limited specialization of the hemispheres, and involvement of deep stem structures in the process. Based on the obtained data, significant differences were identified in the assessment of kinesthetic praxis, spatial praxis, dynamic praxis, auditory-motor coordination, stereognosis, visual gnosis, auditory-speech memory, and drawing skills depending on the group of patients ($p < 0.001$, $p = 0.015$, $p < 0.001$, respectively) (the method used was Fisher's exact test).

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